

Exploring Anti-*Helicobacter Pylori* Potential of Medicinal Plants Used in Ayurveda – A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

This review comprehensively documents the anti *Helicobacter pylori* potential of 31 plant species selected from the families rutaceae, apocynaceae, fabaceae, and menispermaceae (moonseed family). Few plants belonging to vitaceae, musaceae and astaraceae have also been covered in this review. The Rutaceae (citrus) family serves as a good resource for bioactive compounds such as terpenoids, flavonoids and coumarins. The Apocynaceae (dogbane) family serves as a plentiful resource for various compounds, namely, alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids, flavonoids, glycosides, simple phenols, lactones and hydrocarbons, sterols, lignans, and sugars. Fabaceae (legume) families belong to 3 legume families and are enriched in tannins, dyes, spices, fibre plants, ornamental plants, and medicinal plants. All these families are similar in terms of flowering (angiosperm), dicotyledon, and seed production; however, they differ in terms of fruit type, floral structure and active constituents. This review highlights the structural diversity as well as physiological, pharmacological and clinical efficacy of each 31 plants. In vitis family basically the phytoconstituents belong to the group of flavonoids and monoterpenes. The isolation of compound from citrus family has been mainly phenol rich fractions with substantial presence of flavonoids and coumarins. The liquorice plant was found to be enriched in prenylated compound as well as caffeic acid derivative. Alfalfa has been found to be enriched in saponin, isoflavonoid and coumestral derivatives. Effect of various formulations have also been discussed. Current understanding on clinical efficacy of selected plants have also been documented. Among 31 plants the anti *H. pylori* activity of *Vitis vinifera*, citrus, *Andrographis paniculate*, liquorice, Tamarind have been reviewed in details. Overall, in this review diversity in natural resources in the boundary of four important families are attempted to explain. Combining all knowledges new research interest can be generated in future to avoid gastrointestinal disease-induced morbidity in particular.

Keywords: Medicinal Plants, secondary metabolites, flavonoids, clinical, *Helicobacter pylori*.

INTRODUCTION

The prevalence of gastric cancer with the co-occurrence of *H. pylori* has been documented by scientists around the world (1). Out of the 44 studies from 17 countries revealed a 17.4% frequency of *H. pylori*-positive gastric cancer, with a relatively high incidence in Asia (1). The risk of gastric cancer can be attained via the genetic disposition of both host

factors and bacteria. Mucosal inflammation, followed by chronic gastritis and metaplasia, occurs in sequence over time, leading to no return to gastric carcinogenesis (2). In 2013, Japanese scientists invented strategies to prevent gastric cancer via *H. pylori* eradication therapy followed by endoscopic surveillance. In the Middle East, the incidence of gastric cancer was the highest in Iran, followed by Israel, with a very low incidence in Egypt. They

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typically carry infection from childhood. Chronic gastritis remains a risk factor for the development of gastric cancer even after the eradication of *H. pylori* (3,6). The development of gastric cancer occurs via genetic and epigenetic alterations in *H. pylori*-infected gastric mucosa (4,5). Korean gastroenterologists have divided gastric cancer into several forms: overall (OGC), cardia (CGC), noncardia (NGC), early (EGC), advanced, intestinal (IGC), and diffuse forms. In Korean populations, the highest risk was associated with CGC as well as the EGC form. In a Japanese study, *H. pylori* eradication significantly reduced the risk for the development of gastric cancer. Studies involving healthy and infected individuals bearing CagA⁺ and CagA genes revealed a vulnerable risk of gastric cancer with cagA⁺ gene prevalence. Another study revealed a decreased relative risk of gastric cancer when *H. pylori* eradication therapy is ineffective. The relative risk of death was also lower, as was the risk of developing future gastric metaplasia, when eradication therapy was continued. In another study involving a Mongolian population with 45 gastric cancer patients, 53.3% of patients had cancer located in the upper part of the stomach, 37.8% had cancer in the gastric body, and 8.9% had cancer in the lower part of the stomach. The diffuse type of cancer was predominant (60%), whereas the intestinal type (36.7%) and indeterminate type (3.3%) were reported. One hundred percent of the cancer patients were CagA positive, whereas 81% were positive for noncancer patients (10). An Italian study highlighted the potential benefit of eradicating *H. pylori* in the regression of gastric cancer. Furthermore, other gastric microbiomes play limited roles in the development of gastric cancer. In addition to *H. pylori*, dietary carcinogens, Epstein–Barr virus, bile reflux, and autoimmune gastritis can lead to gastric cancer (11).

1.1 *Helicobacter pylori* and virulence factor:

The virulence factors involved in the risk of gastric cancer are urease enzymes, flagella, outer membrane proteins, cagA, VacA, type IV secretion systems, etc. The destruction of the stem cell lineage or renewal by *H. pylori* has been documented as a pivotal instrumental factor in the induction of gastric cancer. The leading causes of these events are replicative, hereditary and environmental. In another study with

248 patients with bile reflux gastritis and gastric cancer, 35.8% were *H. pylori* positive in the bile reflux gastritis group, whereas 73% were *H. pylori* positive in the gastric cancer patient group. The involvement of *H. pylori* in the modulation of immune checkpoint inhibition has also been demonstrated. *H. pylori* infection results in the suppression of dendritic cell and macrophage activity and reduces CD8⁺ T-cell activity. *H. pylori* colonization upregulated T-cell markers and dampened proinflammatory Th1 and Th17 expression. Infection alters the tumor immune microenvironment. *H. pylori* infection increases the concentration of PD-L1 in both gastric and immune cells. *H. pylori* infection alters Th1–Th2 balance and dampens the T-cell-mediated immune system. *H. pylori* infection also stimulates gastric and immune cells to secrete proinflammatory cytokines such as IL-6, IL-8, TNF- α , and IL-1 β . Infection also increases the secretion of immunosuppressive cytokines such as TGF- β and IL-10 (12,13,14).

1. *H. pylori* treatment

Maastricht VI/Florence Consensus Report recommends bismuth-containing quadruple therapy (BQT), consisting of a PPI and two antimicrobial agents plus bismuth, or quadruple concomitant therapy using a PPI and three antimicrobial agents (amoxicillin, clarithromycin, and nitroimidazole) for the same duration as the primary treatment. PPI-based standard triple therapy (STT) is recommended only in areas with a clarithromycin-resistant strain rate of $\leq 15\%$. 14-day duration of eradication recommended by the guidelines. Besides, Kyoto Global Consensus Report, the Sixth Chinese National Consensus Report, all recommend the eradication of *H. pylori* infection. Recently the efficacy of standard triple therapy globally has fall below 80%. Recently, it has been reported that vonoprazan, when combined with 2 antibiotics, is more effective than PPIs used with a similar antibiotic combination (18,19,20). Vonoprazan has advantage of rapid action and no food effect. Probiotics has also been used as supplementary treatment in *H. pylori* eradication therapy with advantage of higher eradication and lesser side effect. Potassium competitive acid blocker do not need activation in the acidic stomach and block the gastric proton pump in both the resting and activated stages; first dose is only effective and longer duration is

achieved. Half life of vonoprazan is 6-8 h. it also ensures stable efficacy in different genetic background. Further options should be reserved for patients with *H. pylori* who are difficult to treat. Traditional Chinese medicine has proved its efficacy in eradication of *H. pylori*. Further, vaccination induced protection is also important to explore. (15-24).

Highlights of the Review:

Antibiotic resistance, poor compliance, reduced gastric pH, high bacterial load, and the rapid metabolism of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) in the human body pose threats to the use of conventional medicine. The search for alternative medicines from

Indian medicinal plants has always been a holistic approach. This review comprehensively documents the anti-infective potential of 31 compounds selected from the families Rutaceae, Apocynaceae, Fabaceae and Menispermaceae (moonseed family). The phytochemical constituents of each family as well as ethnobotany were attempted to explain in details in general followed by their anti-infective potential. The similarity as well as dissimilarity of each families were elaborated. A set of 31 plant (Table 1) having importance in ayurveda use were further explored for their phytochemical constituents as well as anti *Helicobacter pylori* activity. Further the efficacy of important plants in clinical trial has also been explained.

Table 1: List of plants described in the review

Sl.No.	Plant name	Family
1.	Zanthoxylum armatum	Rutaceae
2.	Citrus lemon	
3.	Aegle marmelos	
4.	Glycerrhiza glabra	Fabaceae
5.	Medicago sativa	
6.	Indigofera tinctoria	
7.	Cassia angustifolia	
8.	Tamarindus indica	
9.	Clitoria ternata	
10.	Desmodium gangeticum	
11.	Tephrosia purpurea	
12.	Albizia lebbeck	
13.	Caesalpinia bonduc	
14.	Seshbania grandiflora	
15.	Mucuna pruriens	
16.	Calotropis procera	Apocynaceae
17.	Calotropis gigantean	
18.	Alstonia scholaris	
19.	Rauvolfia serpentina	
20.	Catharanthus roseus	
21.	Hemidesmus indicus	
22.	Holarrhena floribunda	

23.	Thevetia peruviana	
24.	Tinospora cordifolia	Menispermaceae
25.	Cissampelos pareira	
26.	Andrographis paniculata	
27.	Phyllanthus niruri	
28.	Emblica officinalis	
29.	Vitis Vinifera	Vitaceae
30.	Musa sapientum	Musaceae
31.	Matricaria chamomilla	Astaraceae

2. Similarity and dissimilarity between the four families:

In India, the floral and vegetative structure of the Apocynaceae family is typified by woody, laticiferous climbers or shrubs, such as *Ichnocarpus frutescens*, which produces follicles as fruit, has opposite simple leaves, flowers with tubular to funnel-shaped (connate) corollas, and emits creamy latex (165). Fabaceae are readily recognized by their compound leaves, nitrogen-fixing root nodules produced via symbiosis with rhizobia, and distinctive zygomorphic "pea-type" blooms that mature into dehiscent legume pods—key evolutionary adaptations promoting survival in nitrogen-poor soils (166). Rutaceae, exemplified in India by *Citrus* and related genera, exhibit aromatic, gland-dotted (pellucid) leaves; generally, actinomorphic flowers with free petals and sepals, numerous stamens, and a superior, syncarpous ovary; and highly varied fruit types—hesperidia, drupes, berries, and capsules—reflecting the family's remarkable diversity (3). Menispermaceae, which is not well known for Indian plants, usually includes climbing lianas with simple leaves that alternate, small actinomorphic flowers, and drupe-like fruits that often have unique crescent-shaped seeds (menisperm) that set them apart from the legumes of Fabaceae and the follicles of Apocynaceae. Therefore, even though all four families have woody or shrubby habits and ancestral actinomorphic floral features in India, they are very different from each other: Fabaceae, with its compound leaves, nodules, zygomorphic flowers, and legumes; Apocynaceae, with latex, opposite simple leaves, and follicles;

Rutaceae, with aromatic, glandular leaves and highly variable superior ovary fruit types; and Menispermaceae, with climbing habits and curved-seeded drupes.

3 Phytochemical investigation of individual plants

3.1 Vitis Varieties:

The members of this family are collectively termed grapevines. The family contains approximately 1000 species assigned to 17 genera that are typically shrubs or woody lianas that climb by means of their leaf-opposed tendrils—hence the name Vitaceae (Latin *viere*=to attach). Vitaceae roots are generally fibrous and well branched, and they can grow to several meters in length. The leaves are alternate, except during the juvenile phase of plants grown from seeds, and can be simple or composite. The fruits are usually fleshy berries with one to four seeds. (170)

3.1.1. *Vitis vinifera*: (grapes)

Vitis varieties are wind pollinated with hermaphroditic flowers containing both male and female reproductive structures, whereas wild species are dioecious. These flowers are grouped into bunches called inflorescences. It is a vigorous, deciduous, climbing shrub that produces woody stems that can be 15–20 m long. The plant attaches itself to the surrounding vegetation via coiled tendrils. In addition to its food value, the plant also has a range of other edible and medicinal uses as well as supplies dyes, oils, cream of tartars and wood. The parts used were

fruit, leaves, young tendrils, seeds, sap, and cream of tartar (for making back powder).

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) in grapevines (*Vitis vinifera* L.) encompass a broad spectrum of analytes that contribute to the distinctive aroma of each grape variety. The majority of volatile compounds are terpenoids, with monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes representing the primary constituents. Terpenoids typically exist in two forms: free or glycosylated derivatives. Free terpenoids are known to directly contribute to grape aroma. Various factors, including fruit ripening stage and grape variety, influence the terpenoid compositions of grapes and wines. The alcoholic extract of *Vitis vinifera* leaves has been reported to contain flavonol glycosides and glucuronides, Myricetin (1), quercetin (2),

kaempferol (3), and isorhamnetin (4). (25) Bioactivity-guided fractionation of raisins revealed presence of triterpenoids (seven natural and three novel). The novel triterpenoids are 3 β ,13 β -dihydroxy-12,13-dihydrooleanolic acid, 3 β ,12 β ,13 β -trihydroxy-12,13-dihydrooleanolic acid, and 3 β ,13 β -dihydroxy-12,13-dihydroursolic acid (27). In another study, bioactivity-guided fractionation of an ethanolic extract of *Vitis* led to the isolation of resveratrol, 11-O-acetyl bergenin, and stigmast-4-en-3-one (26). In another study, low speed counter-current chromatography of grapevine shoot extract Vineatrol 30 led to the isolation of active molecules like *trans*- ϵ -viniferin, *r*-2-viniferin, hopeaphenol, and miyabenol C having anticancer activity (28). (Figure 1)

Figure 1: Active constituents from *Vitis vinifera*

Myricetin (1)		
Quercetin (2)		
Kaempferol (3)		
Isorhamnetin (4)		

3.2 *Musa sapientum* (Banana)

Musaceae is a small family comprises on six genera (*Strelitzia*, *Ravenala*, *Musa*, *Orchidantha*, *Ensete* and *Heliconia*) and 130 species whereas some phanerogamists recognize Musaceae comprises only on two genera *Musa* and *Ensete*. Plants belong to

Musaceae family having berry fruits, inferior ovary, inflorescence spadix covered by a spathe, zygomorphic flowers, forming crown at the apex of stout unbranched stem, large leaves and perennial giant herbs appearing like trees (Sharma, 2011). Banana is the most common plant of this family. (171)

Musa species grow in a wide range of environments and have varied human uses, ranging from edible bananas and plantains of the tropics to cold-hardy fibre and ornamental plants. *Musa sapientum* is a large, perennial herbaceous plant in the Musaceae family. *Musa sapientum* possesses various medicinal properties that are beneficial for health. Fruit digestion, diarrhea treatment, constipation, gastric ulcers, and high potassium content increase blood pressure and support cardiac health. Unripe fruit can control diabetes; stem juice detoxifies the body, purifies blood, regresses kidney stones, promotes wound healing, and has anticancer, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory effects. The active constituents are flavonoids, phenolics, and dopamine (29).

3.3 *Zanthoxylum armatum* (Tajabati)

Zanthoxylum species grow as tall or small trees or as scandent or erect shrubs. They are usually recognizable by their citrus-like fragrance and glandular dots on their leaves, and most species are characterized by prickles of varying sizes on their trunks, branches, and/or leaves. The genus is predominantly distributed in the Himalayas, America, and Africa, as well as Central, South, Southeast, and East Asia. The plants in the genus are excellent sources of edible fruits, oils, culinary, and high-value wood. *Zanthoxylum armatum* DC. The name “Timur or Toothache tree” is a high-value medicinal plant known for its aromatic, cultural, and economic significance. The aromatic bark is used as a fish poison and insect repellent. Oil is obtained from dried fruits via steam distillation and is used in the perfume industry. Twigs are used as toothbrushes and walking sticks. Bark, fruit, and seeds are carminative, stomachic, and anthelmintic; fruits are used to treat dental trouble (168).

3.4 *Citrus lemon*:

The fruit eaten fresh and the acid juice, rind and zest are used in a variety of foods and drinks. Citric acid, pectin and lemon oil are byproducts. Fruits are pickled. The most common fruit associated with assamese kitchens, a major source of vitamin C, is highly antibacterial, has improved digestion, and can be used as a remedy for worms. The phenolic-rich fraction was successfully identified as the main effective component of *C. aurantium*. Sixty-five

components were identified from the 40% ethanol eluent of the phenol-rich fraction. The five components ultimately obtained were feruloylagmatine (5), haplotype C (6), sagittatin A (7), linderagalactone C (8) and koparin-2'-methyl ether (9) (30). Leaf extracts of four varieties of *C. paradisi* in petroleum ether, chloroform, methanol and water followed by fractionation and purification of the methanolic extract led to the identification of four compounds, namely, myricetin (1), rutin (10), quercetin (3), and kaempferol (2) (31). Nine coumarins were isolated from the methanolic extract of *C. junos* seed shells, namely, xanthotoxin (11), imperatorin, isogosferol (12), heraclenol (13), isopimpinellin (14), byakangelicin (15), heraclenol-3-methyl ether, umbelliferon (16), and umbelliferon-7-O--l-rhamnopyranosyl(1,2)--d-glucopyranoside (33). Bitter orange (*Citrus aurantium*) is an important source of essential oils with high antimicrobial activities. Coumarins and flavones were the most abundant classes of compounds in the high-value fractions responsible for up to 61% of the mycelial inhibition of *F. jinanense* (32). Bioactivity-guided fractionation, a new flavanone triglycoside, naringenin 7-O-(2",6"-di-O-alpha-rhamnopyranosyl)-beta-glucopyranoside, and hesperetin 7-O-(2",6"-di-O-alpha-rhamnopyranosyl)-beta-glucopyranoside, hesperidin (17) and narirutin (18) have been isolated from the fruits of *Citrus junos* Tanaka (Rutaceae). In addition, hesperetin 7-O-(2",6"-di-O-alpha-rhamnopyranosyl)-beta-glucopyranoside (2) has been shown to have antiinfluenza activity (36). The results of the bioactivity-guided test revealed that the butanol (BA) and ethyl acetate (EA) liquid-liquid extraction of the ethanol extract of lemons led to the discovery of moieties such as the antiplatelet activity of four marker compounds, namely, oxypeucedanin hydrate (19), citric acid, diosmin (20), and limetin (21), which have antiplatelet activity (33). The whole fruit of *C. depressa* was subjected to ethanol extraction, followed by partitioning to obtain water, butanol, and ethyl acetate fractions, allowing the discovery of SARS-CoV-2 spike protein inhibitors (35). Phytochemical analysis of citrus lemon essential oil (CL) revealed that its major compounds are two monoterpenes, limonene (22) and pinene (23). Limonene (LIM) is a major constituent of several citrus oils. It has been used for the relief of heartburn

and gastroesophageal reflux disorders because of its ability to neutralize gastric acid and improve peristalsis. It has also demonstrated chemopreventive activity against many types of cancer, including gastric and colorectal cancer (37). N-LFCs (natural

linear furano coumarins) are phytochemicals that are present in many botanical groups, most notably the citrus family *Rutaceae* and the carrot family *Apiaceae* (38,39). (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Active constituents from Citrus lemon

Feruloylagmatine (5)	<p>C18325</p>	
Haploside C (6)		
Sagittatin A (7)		
Linderagalactone C (8)		
Koparin-2'-methyl ether (9)		

Rutin (10)			
Xanthotoxin (11)			
Isogosferol (12)			
Heraclenol (13)			
Isopimpinellin (14)			
Byakangelicin (15)			

Umbelliferone (16)			
Hesperidine (17)			
Narirutin (18)			
oxypeucedanin hydrate (19)			
Diosmine (20)			
Limettin (21)			

Limonine (22)		
α -Pinene (23)		
naringenin (24)		

3.5 *Matricaria chamomilla*

The Asteraceae family, often known as the sunflower family, is one of the largest flowering plant families, including over 1600 genera and 25,000 species worldwide. It includes a number of well-known species, such as chicory, sunflower, lettuce, coreopsis, dahlias and daisy, as well as a number of plants of medicinal significance, such as wormwood, chamomile and dandelion. (172) Chamomalie is an ancient herb used to calm down anxiety and treat stomach troubles. This herb is native to Germany, Egypt, Italy, Spain, France, Eastern Europe, and Morocco. Dried flowers of the herb constitutes flavonoids, terpenoids. Most of these species are used as herbal infusions or teas (40,41).

3.6 *Aegle marmelos*:

Aegle marmelos is a slow-growing, medium-sized, spiny tree that is up to 12–15 m tall. The species has deciduous trifoliolate leaves, and its flowers are bisexual. It occurs in dry forests on hills and plains, as well as in mixed deciduous and dry dipterocarp forests (Orwa et al. 2009). This species has a history of being planted extensively for wasteland management owing to its adaptability to acidic and alkaline soils.

3.7. *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (Fabaceae)

The liquorice plant is a perennial herb (42). The flower of liquorice comes mainly from anethole, i.e.,

glycyrrhizic acid. Licorice may be useful for treating mouth ulcers and peptic ulcers. In a study, twenty-six phenolic compounds were obtained from the ethyl acetate partition of an ethanol extract of the aerial parts of *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* Fisch. Eight prenylated phenolic compounds (glycyuralins Q-X) (26) with activities against the SARS-CoV-2 virus protease 3CL^{pro} were obtained (43). In another study, thin layer chromatography bioautography (using DPPH spray reagent)-guided fractionation of *Glycyrrhiza glabra* led to the isolation of two caffeic acid derivative esters, viz. Eicosanyl caffeate (27) and docosyl caffeate (28) have potent elastase inhibitory activities (44). The methanol extract of *G. uralensis* roots and its chloroform fraction exhibit anti-HCV activity (45). For bioactivity-guided purification and structural analysis, glycycomarin (29), glycyrin (30), glycyrol (31) and liquiritigenin (32) were isolated and identified as anti-HCV compounds. Glycyrrhizin (33), the major constituent of *G. uralensis*, and its monoammonium salts, licochalcone A (34) and glabridin (35), which are known to be exclusive constituents of *G. inflata* and *G. glabra*, have marginal activity. Another chalcone, isoliquiritigenin (36), has good activity. The total MeOH extract and CHCl₃, EtOAc, n-buOH and rH₂O subextracts were prepared from *G. iconica* roots. A new dihydrochalcone, iconichalcone (1), along with 15 known phenolic compounds, was isolated from the active CHCl₃, EtOAc and n-buOH subextracts. Among these compounds, licoricidin (37), dehydroglyasperin C

(38), iconisoflaven and 1-methoxyficifolinol (39) were found to be the most active compounds in the treatment of cancer (46). The chemical composition of three *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. (licorice) leaf extracts obtained through maceration or ultrasound-assisted

methods (fresh and dried leaves) was investigated. Guided fractionation yielded three main components: pinocembrin (40), glabranin (41) and licoflavanone (42), which constitute new scaffolds for anti-inflammatory drug research (47). (Figure 3)

Figure 3: Active constituents from Glycyrrhiza glabra

glycyrrhizic acid (25) Glycyralin E (26)		
eicosanyl caffeate (27)		
Docosyl caffeate (28)		
Glycycoumarin (29)		
Glycyrin (30)		

Glycyrol (31)	<p>The chemical structure of Glycyrol (31) is a complex polycyclic molecule. It features a central chromone-like core with a lactone ring fused to it. The structure includes several hydroxyl groups (OH) and a methoxy group (OCH₃). A side chain with a terminal vinyl group is also present.</p>	
Liquiritigenin (32)	<p>The chemical structure of Liquiritigenin (32) is a flavone. It consists of a chromone core with a hydroxyl group at the 7-position and a p-coumaroyl group at the 3-position.</p>	
Glycyrrhizin (33)	<p>The chemical structure of Glycyrrhizin (33) is a complex triterpene saponin. It features a pentacyclic triterpene aglycone core with multiple hydroxyl groups and a glycosidic linkage to a trisaccharide chain.</p>	
Licochalcone A (34)	<p>The chemical structure of Licochalcone A (34) is a chalcone. It consists of a chalcone core with a methoxy group at the 5-position and a vinyl group at the 2-position.</p>	
Glabridine (35)	<p>The chemical structure of Glabridine (35) is a coumarin. It features a coumarin core with a methoxy group at the 7-position and a p-coumaroyl group at the 3-position.</p>	

isoliquiritigenin (36)		
Licoricidin (37)		
dehydroglyasperin C (38)		
1-methoxyficifolinol (39)		
Pinocembrin (40)		

Glabranin (41)		
Licoflavanone (42)		

3.8 *Medicago sativa* (alfalfa or lucerna)

It is cultivated as an important forage crop. It is native to a warmer therapeutic climate. Alfalfa (*M. sativa*) is best known as a crop for animal feed; however, its ability to reduce cholesterol levels via its saponins and use it as a phytoestrogen on the basis of its isoflavonoid and coumestrol contents has been intensively researched. Since it contains non-protein amino acid canavanine, it can induce systemic lupus erythematosus-like syndrome [12]. In cosmetics, extracts of aerial parts, seeds and isolated unsaponifiables are used (77)

3.9 *Indigofera tinctoria*

True indigo is an erect shrub. True indigo is used for glowing skin, sores, ringworms, blisters, hair rejuvenation, natural hair darkening, removing worms in teeth and gums, and soreing on the skin, liver, etc. It is the resource for blue indigo dye from leaves.

3.10 *Cassia angustifolia*

Indian senna is a woody perennial herb. Senna alexandrina is used in the form of senna pods or as an herbal tea laxative. The active ingredients are senna glycosides, which interact with immune cells in the colon. Bioassay-guided fractionation led to the isolation and identification of a known bioactive compound, luteolin (43). *Singueana* is a promising candidate for the development of poultry phytogetic feed additives. (Figure 4)

Figure 4: Active constituents from *Cassia angustifolia*

3.11 *Tamarindus indica*

Tamarindas indica is a large perennial tree that is often cultivated as an ornamental and shaded tree because of its timber and fruits. There are five compounds present in the bioactive fraction of *Tamarindus indica*, namely, n-decanoic acid, n-tridecanoic acid, 1-(+)-ascorbic acid, 2,6-dihexadecanoate, methyl trans-9-octadecanoate, and octa-9-enoic acid, which inhibits *Trypanosoma evansi* protein-tyrosine phosphatase via the stem bark bioactive fraction of *Tamarindus indica*. Stem bark extract of *Tamarindus indica* was obtained using n-hexane and methanol (3:2) as the solvent system (49)

3.12. *Clitoria ternate* (blue pea)

In Indian Ayurveda, it is commonly known by the name Aparajita. It is a perennial herbaceous plant with elliptic, obtuse leaves. Triterpenoids, flavanol glycosides, anthocyanins, steroids. Clitoides,

terpenes, and polyacylated derivatives of delphinidin 3,3",5"-triglucose are abundant (50) (Figure 5)

Figure 5: Active constituents from *Clitoria ternate*

3.13. *Desmodium gangeticum*

Shalpani is a component of the Dashmula group. It has marked analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity. Roots contain resin, alkaloids, and essential oils (56)

3.14. *Albizia lebbek*

Lebbeck is a deciduous, perennial, medium-sized legume tree. It is an efficient N-fixing legume that nodulates abundantly without needing seed inoculation. It is used to remove contaminant turbidity

from surface water by its coagulant activity (57). It contains phytochemicals such as alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, and terpenoids.

3.15. *Caesalpinia bonduc* (Fever nut)

It climbs up to 15 m long. Fruits are tonic and antipyretic. Seeds yield a fatty oil used as a cosmetic and for discharge from the ear. Leaves and bark are febrifuge. Cassane furanoditerpene and flavonoids are abundant. The crude plant extract has wide use in ethnomedicine as antihyperglycemic as well as antimicrobial (58, 59)

3.16. *Seshbania grandiflora*

It is a short-lived, soft-wounded, loosely branching tree with a rather open crown. A true multipurpose tree, providing a range of foods, medicines, timber, gum and tannins. Leaves are aperient, diuretic. Bitter bark are astringent, febrifuge, tonic, antipyretic, remedy for gastric troubles, colic with diarrhea and dysentery. Flowers are emollient and laxative, and the root is a well-known medicine for treating malaria. (Figure 6)

Figure 6: Active constituents from *Seshbania grandiflora*

Honokiol (46)		
Isomagnolol (47)		

The known compounds were identified as 4'-O-methyl honokiol (44), magnolol (45), honokiol (46), 3-methoxymagnolol, isomagnolol (47), and ketone, which have antimalarial activity. The dried and powdered twigs and fruit of *M. grandiflora* (175 g) were exhaustively extracted with MeOH in two 24-hour percolation steps followed by partitioning into hexane, methylene chloride and aqueous methanolic fractions. The latter was detanninized by passage through a column of polyvinyl pyrrolidone to obtain the active methanolic fraction 0038279-03C, X-4568. Bioactivity-guided fractionation afforded 4-O-methylhonokiol (**1**), magnolol (**2**), and honokiol (**3**), which bind more strongly to cannabinoids than to opioids (52,53,54,55).

3.17. *Mucuna pruriens* (Velvet bean)

Velvet bean (*M. pruriens*) is a leguminous vine. They have three main uses: food, feed (forage and seeds) and environmental services. Velvet bean can be beneficial since it is high in levodopa, which helps maintain healthy cholesterol and blood sugar levels. The seed powder is used for parkinsonism disease. It can increase the production of human growth hormone. *Mucuna pruriens* (family: Fabaceae) are mentioned in the Indian traditional system of Ayurveda medicine to possess androgenic activity and increase male virility. In addition, plants have been reported to improve testosterone levels and sperm production in experimental male rodents. Column chromatography

and TLC analysis (ethanolic extraction of MM seeds) yielded 14 fractions. GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of 9,12-octadecadienoic acid (Z,Z)- (ODDA) (48) in MM13 (60) (Figure 7)

Figure 7; Active constituents *Mucuna pruriens*

3.18 *Calotropis procera*

Calotropis is a spreading shrub or medium-sized tree that reaches 2.5 to 6 m in height. It is a multipurpose tree. The milk sap has been renewed for its ethnomedicinal properties. It is used as a fodder. A bioassay-guided fractionation of the crude flavonoid fraction (Cf3) of the MeOH extract from *Calotropis procera*, which presented the highest antimicrobial activity, led to the isolation of four flavonoid glycosides as bioactive constituents. 3-O-Rutinosides (49) of quercetin, kaempferol and isorhamnetin, in addition to the flavonoid 5-hydroxy-3,7-dimethoxyflavone-4'-O- β -glucopyranoside, have antibacterial activity. The gram-positive bacteria

(*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis*) were more susceptible than the gram-negative bacteria (*Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Salmonella enteritidis*), and the yeast species were more susceptible than the filamentous fungi antileishmanial. The traditional anti-sickling herbal medicines FACA[®] and DREPANOSTAT[®], which are composed of *Zanthoxylum zanthoxyloides* (Lam.) Zepern. & Timler (Rutaceae) and *Calotropis procera* (Aiton) Dryand. (Apocynaceae). (64,65,66) (Figure 8)

Figure 8: Active constituents from *Calotropis procera*

3.19 *Calotropis gigantea* (crown flower)

Calotropis gigantea is a fast-growing, attractive, evergreen flowering shrub or small tree that grows approximately 5 m tall, occasionally up to 10 m tall. *Calotropis gigantea* is especially valued as a medicinal plant and source of fibre. The milky sap (latex) coagulates when warm and possesses cardiotonic, antiseptic, emetic, purgative, vermifuge, dysentery, leprosy, epilepsy, asthma, and antiemetic properties. The bark, leaves, flowers, and juice of young buds all have medicinal properties.

Figure 9: Active constituents from *Calotropis gigantea*

Bioactivity-guided isolation of the CHCl_3 -soluble fraction of the roots of *Calotropis gigantea* was carried out to obtain a new cardenolide glycoside, caloside G (50). Extracts from the root bark of *Calotropis gigantea* were subjected to bioactivity-guided fractionation via growth inhibitory effects against *Entamoeba histolytica*. The n-hexane-soluble portion of the chloroform extract showed in vitro antiamoebic activity against the HK-9 strain of *Entamoeba histolytica*. Chromatographic separation of the chloroform extract afforded the known compound, procersterol, which showed activity against *E. histolytica*. (67, 68)

3.20. *Hemidesmus indicus* (Indian Sarsaparilla – anantmoool)

Indian sarsaparilla is a vine that trails on the ground and climbs by means of tendrils growing in pairs from the petioles of the alternate, orbicular to ovate, evergreen leaves. It is anabolic in its activity and is useful for treating venereal disease, herpes, skin diseases, arthritis, rheumatism, gout, epilepsy, insanity, chronic nervous disease, abdominal distension, intestinal gas, debility, impotence and turbid urine. Phytochemical analysis and thin layer chromatography (TLC) bioautography of the crude extracts revealed the presence of alkaloids, phenols and flavonoids as active phytoconstituents with activity against extended-spectrum β -lactamase-producing bacteria. (68,69,70,71)

3.21. *Thevetia peruviana*

Thevetia peruviana is an evergreen shrub or small tree that is usually 3–8 m tall with a short hole. The main medically active compounds found in the plant include a range of cardiac glycosides, peruvoside, and Thevetin A. The latex, bark, seeds, and infusion of the roots all have medicinal value. (72, 73)

3.22 *Cissampelos pareira*

The velvet leaf is a small climber with velvety branches. It is known as a midwife's herb and is used mainly for women's ailments, menstrual problems, hormonal imbalances, ease of childbirth, postpartum pain, threatened miscarriages, uterine hemorrhages, heart problems, kidney stones, kidney infections, asthma, arthritis, muscle cramps, and stomach pain

(74,75). A number of active compounds such as alkaloids, saponins, glycosides, carbohydrates, tannins, phenolics, flavonoids, steroids, protein, amino acids, triterpenoids, and lignins are abundant.

3.23 *Phyllanthus niruri*

It is an erect, annual plant that often branches from the base and grows 15–50 cm tall. The roots, leaves, fruits, milky juice, and whole plants have medicinal value. It is considered acrid, colling, diuretic, thirst, bronchitis, leprosy, anaemia, urinar discharge, anuria, biliousness, and asthma (76). The family is rich in phytochemicals such as tannins, terpenes, alkaloids, glycosidic compounds, saponins, and flavones.

4. Traditional uses in Ayurvedic system of medicine:

The *H. pylori* infection are manifested with abdominal pain, nausea, bloating, loss of appetite, fatigue and others in human beings. These symptoms resemble with two diseases Grahani Roga and Gulma Roga mentioned in Ayurveda. Many medicinal plants belong to Apocynaceae, Fabaceae, Menispermaceae and Rutaceae families are mentioned to be effective for management of Grahani Roga and Gulma Roga. *Aegle marmelos* (Bilva), *Vitis vinifera* (Draksha) from Vitaceae family; *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (Yastimadhu), *Medicago sativa* (Ashwabala), *Cassia angustifolia* (Swarnapatri) from Fabaceae family; *Alstonia scholaris* (Saptaparna), *Holarrhena antidysenterica* (Kutaja), *Calotropis procera* (Arka) from Apocynaceae family; and *Emblica officinalis* (Amlaki), *Phyllanthus niruri* (Bhumi Amlaki), *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegha), *Tinospora cordifolia* (Guduchi) from Menispermaceae family are mentioned to have activities against Grahani Roga in the ancient texts of Ayurveda. The medicinal plants from Rutaceae family, *A. marmelos* (Bilva) and *V. vinifera* (Draksha) are effective for management of Gulma Roga (160). Many Ayurvedic formulations such as Triphala Churna, Avipattikara Churna, Hingwastaka Churna, Bilvadi Vati, Chitrakadi Vati, Kamdudha Rasa, Sutashekhara Rasa and others containing these medicinal plants as ingredient are mentioned for management of *H. pylori* infection like symptoms (161). Many research works have been carried out by taking these medicinal plants to combat *H. pylori* in traditional Ayurvedic system of medicine.

Yastimadhu (*G. glabra*) was found to have significant effects to heal the ulcer by protecting the mucus membrane, and to inhibit the bacterial growth (162). *Sharapunkha* (*T. purpurea*) exhibited antiulcer and anti-inflammatory effects against multi-drug resistant *H. pylori* infection (163). Methanolic extract of *Bael* (*A. marmelos*) had shown significant gastro-protective and antiulcer effects against *H. pylori* lipopolysaccharide induced oxidative stress in rats (5).

5. Anti-*Helicobacter pylori* activity

5.1 *Vitis vinifera*

The anti-*H. pylori* activity of table and muscadine varieties was evaluated by Brown et al.(169) (dose range 256–2048 µg/ml). In a study involving muscadine grape extracts, skin extracts, and seed extracts, synergistic extract MIC values ranging from 256–1024 µg/ml were observed; the skin extracts exhibited more potent activity than did the seed extracts. Furthermore, the extract promoted *H. pylori* AGS cell growth in a concentration- and time-dependent manner better than did resveratrol and ellagic acid (skin extract > synergy > seed) when it was applied to strains 26695 and SS1. A similar result was obtained in a cell cytotoxicity assay using infected AGS cells. The ability of the skin extract (1024--4096 µg/ml) to inhibit adhesion was powerful. In another study, hydroalcoholic extracts of colonine, sangiovese and cabernet sauvignon grape cultivars were evaluated against *H. pylori* g21 (cagA⁻) and 10K (cagA⁺) clinical isolates, and the reported MIC values were borderline (i.e., MICs of 1.35–3.57 µg/ml). The pathogenic strain itself was less susceptible, suggesting the need for synergistic therapy with antibiotics in the future.(80) In another study, *Vitis vinifera* leaf extract and the compounds isolated from quercetin-3-O-glucuronide butyl ester showed potent anti-*H. pylori* activity (2–5 µg/ml); the strains used were G27, 7.13, J99, 26695, SS1, and ATCC 51652.(81) Wine describes a yeast fermentation product of the must, or juice, pressed from grapes, the fruit of the species *Vitis vinifera*. In mice infected with SPM 326 (a Type I *H. pylori* strain expressing Sa/ma vacA), red wine and green tea significantly reduced the gastritis score. Immunohistochemistry revealed that *H. pylori* was visible only in the superficial layer

of the mucosa.(82) Green tea was found to be relatively effective in ameliorating vacA-induced gastritis.(83) In another study, Chilean red wine also exhibited in vitro anti-*H. pylori* activity.(84) Furthermore, Italian red wine has also exhibited in vitro anti-*H. pylori* activity. (85) In another study, red wine and green tea reduced vacA-induced current in a planar bilayer experiment.(86, 87)

5.2 Citrus lemon:

The biflavonoid hesperitin-7-rhamnoglucoside from citrus uranium fruit peel inhibited *H. pylori* urease in a competitive and concentration-dependent manner. (88) key lime (*Citrus amantifolia*) has also been shown to potentially inhibit *H. pylori* growth via ATCC 43526 and a triple drug-resistant strain (TDR) (1;64 dil), resulting in 18.77% inhibition of *H. pylori* urease. The TDR strain exhibited 2.62% inhibition at a 1:128 dilution. The active constituent citral, 4-hexen-3-one, exhibited both anti-*H. pylori* and anti-urea activity, but palmitic acid and oleic acid exhibited no inhibitory effects. The extent of attenuation with ATCC 43526 was approximately 1:64 greater than that with the TDR strain, i.e., 1:128.(89) In another study, bergamot juice (*Citrus bergamia*) exhibited 50–90% inhibition when doses between 2.5–5% were used (as well as synergy with AMX and MTZ); no synergy was observed with clarithromycin. 10BJ juice at 20% inhibited the growth of bacteria (entirely) after 6 h (cagA+) and 2 h (CagA-) in a time-kill kinetic study.(90) Auraptene (7-geranyloxycoumarin) obtained from citrus fruits (*Citrus paradisi*) has been found to be effective as an antiadhesive. It strongly suppressed CD74 expression and disrupted serum starvation-induced extracellular signalling-regulated kinase (ERK) I/II activation, antiadhesion and downregulation of IL-8 expression.(91) It also markedly attenuated *H. pylori* colonization and gastritis by inhibiting CD74, macrophage migration inhibitory factor, interleukin 1 β , tumor necrosis factor, and serum macrophage inhibitory protein-2 in the gastric mucosa.(92) *Citrus amantifolia* (IC₅₀ of 28 μ g/ml) also inhibited Jack bean urease. (93) Nobiletin, a polymethoxylated flavonoid in citrus fruits, reduces ROS levels; reduces the level of lipid peroxides and glutathione content; impedes the expression of tumor necrosis factor- α , interleukin 6, cyclooxygenase 2, PI3K, AKT, MAPK,

p38, ERK1, and c-jun amino terminal kinases; attenuates *H. pylori* infection and related activation; and prevents *H. pylori* infection-mediated gastric cancer. Sudachitin and 3'-demethoxysudachitin isolated from *Citrus Sudachi* exhibited potent anti-*H. pylori* activity. (94)

5.3 Aegle marmelos

Aegle marmelos fruit has been shown to ameliorate *H. pylori*-induced (50 μ g/animal) gastritis. At doses between 25 and 500 mg/kg, the extent of reduction ranged between 2.8% and 93.18%.(95)

5.4. Matricaria Recuitta

Matricaria chamomila has been shown to suppress ROS from *H. pylori* infection.(96) The oil extract from M. reculita has shown anti-*H. pylori* activity, with an MIC₉₀ of 125 mg/ml and an MIC₅₀ of 62.5 mg/ml.**Error! Reference source not found.** The antiadhesive activity of the M. reculita flower extract was found to be insignificant, with an IC₅₀ >35 mg/ml against *C. jejuni* (98).

5.5 Andrographis paniculate

Labdane diterpenoids isolated from Andrographis paniculate exhibited potent anti-*H. pylori* activity (MIC of 9 μ g/ml) and urease inhibition, with an IC₅₀ value of 20.2 μ g/ml. (106) combinations of propolis, royal jelly and A. paniculate resulted in increased anti-*H. pylori* activity.(107)

5.6. Tamarindus indica

The ethanolic extract of tamarindus indica (2.5 mg/disc) had an inhibition zone diameter of 3.6 mm, whereas A. paniculate at the same dose produced no inhibition zone. Tamarindus indica (20 strains) presented MIC/MBC values between 12 and 30 mg/ml. (109)

5.7 Glycyrrhiza glabra

G. glabra inhibits *H. pylori* in a dose-dependent manner. A complex of *Lactobacillus paracasei* (2×10^7 CFU), *Perilla frutescens* (15 mg/kg) and *G. glabra* (1.2 mg/kg) inhibited *H. pylori* virulence genes such as Alp A, CagA, FlaA, and UreA. In in vitro infection, the complex also exhibited ameliorating

potential. The complex could also reduce IL-8 levels, demonstrating its potential to treat diseases caused by *H. pylori* infection.(110) *Lactobacillus paracasei* HP7 has shown strong inhibitory potential against *H. pylori* in vitro and in vivo. The complex could increase the villus length. 90% ethanol extract of *G. glabra* exhibited the greatest killing potential (50 µg/ml, IC₅₀ 2.88 µg/ml). Both extracts exhibited synergistic potential in terms of their IC₅₀ values. GutGard, a flavonoid extract of *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, exhibited potent anti-*H. pylori* activity. Glabridin exhibited superior activity, whereas glycyrrhizin, even at 250 µg/ml, exhibited no activity. GutGard showed potential for reducing ³⁵S methionine incorporation and inhibiting DNA gyrase and dihydrofolate reductase (IC₅₀ ~ 3-5 µg/ml) but failed to exhibit any antiadhesive activity.(111) *G. glabra* is known to contain the anti-inflammatory agent 12-keto-triterpeensaponin. Antiadhesive properties were obtained with aqueous extract (1 mg/ml). purified polysaccharides have shown significant anti-*H. pylori* activity as well as antiadhesive activity.(113) HEMCO, an herbal composition consisting of *Asparagus racemosus* (saponins and steroids), *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (glycerol and flavonoids), mentha piperita (Menthol), *Foeniculum vulgare* (trans anethole), *Pimpinella anitum* (anethole and polyphenol) and *tabecaria avellanadae* (lapachol) at 10 mg/disc, exhibited anti-*H. pylori* activity, with an IZD of ~ 22 mm.(114) Krausse et al. evaluated the in vitro anti-*H. pylori* activity of extractum liquiritiae (EL), glycyrrhizic acid (GL), glycyrrhizic acid (GA), a lipophilic derivative of glycyrrhizic acid monoglucuronide (GAMG), and acetylated GAMG (gGAMG). The most active compound was GA (MIC_{50/90} 50–100 µg/ml), whereas GAMG (MIC 400 µg/ml) exhibited rapid, concentration dependent, and strain-dependent bactericidal activity.(115) In another study, special liquorice extracts (s-lico) were shown to potentially ameliorate *H. pylori*-induced angiogenic activity, gastric damage and gastritis, as well as *H. pylori*-induced gastric tumorigenesis.(115) In another study, polysaccharides from *G. glabra* showed potent antiadhesive activity against *H. pylori* and *P. gingivalis* (60–70% inhibition).(116) In a randomized clinical trial on the response of patients (120), all of which are positive against urease, a study revealed that patients receiving licorice with clarithromycin-

based therapy for 2 weeks (83.3%) compared with the control group receiving only clarithromycin.(117) In another study, an oxyprenylated chalcone (xinjiachalcone A) derived from *Glycyrrhiza inflata* Batalin was found to be a relatively effective compound, with low MIC/MBC values against *H. pylori*. (118) Furthermore, the anti-*H. pylori* activity of liquorice from Kembo medicine was investigated in detail. Glabridin, glabrine (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), licochalconen A (*G. inflata*), licoricidin, and licoisoflavone B (*G. uralensis*) exhibited anti-*H. pylori* activity even in Clar- and Amox-resistant strains. Isoflavone compounds obtained from *G. uralensis*, namely, estitol, liquor, 1-methoxyphaseollidin, and gancaonol C, exhibited potent anti-*H. pylori* activity. (119) Licorice mouthwash at 12.5–25% has the potential to inhibit *H. pylori*, where 25% undiluted extract exhibited a maximum inhibition zone.(120) The methyl and ethyl acetate fractions of the methanolic liquorice powder extract exhibited potent antiurease activities ranging from 55.7–100%. Licorice fraction F1 (1 mg/ml) dose-dependently inhibited the growth of bacteria. Complete inhibition was obtained within 6 h. (121)

5.8 Others:

The methanolic extract of *T. purpurea* has shown potent anti-*Helicobacter pylori* activity (Chinniah et al.) (100) Seshbania leaf extract (methanolic) at 240 µg/disc presented ~1.7 cm IZD. The antibacterial activity of *Calotropis procera* was found to be in the range of 16–64 µg/ml (MIC) (102) pet ether, and chloroform and methanolic extracts of leaves of *Calotropis gigantea* exhibited borderline activity, with IZD values of ~ 9.8--13 mm (at 240 µg/disc dose). (105). **Error! Reference source not found.** *Embelica officinalis* at a dose of 800 µg/disc has been shown to have an IZD of ~ 12–14 mm.(103) Another triphala (combination of *Terminalia bellerica*, *Terminalia chebula* and *Embelica officinalis*) presented MICs of ~ 80–320 µg/ml. The combination perturbs the microstructure of *H. pylori* and downregulates adhesion-associated genes and flagellar genes, thereby inhibiting bacterial adhesion, biofilm formation, urease activity and CagA protein expression.(104) *Alstonia boonei* has shown anti-*H. pylori* activity, with MICs ranging from 1.3–7.75 mg/ml. (98) A derivative of N-phenylpropenoyl-L-

amino acids obtained from *C. angustifolia* showed no antiadhesive properties.(106)

6. Review on clinical trial of important herbs:

Vitis vinifera seed extract was assessed for venous relief symptom using double-blind prospective randomized trial with patients from 13 hospitals and found to be inferior to micronized purified flavonoid fraction (MPFF) in relieving venous symptoms and improving quality of life in patients with chronic venous disease. (122). A randomized, double-blind clinical trial was performed on 40 obese or overweight subjects with grape seed extracts (300mg/day) to evaluate the effects of GSE supplementation on inflammatory markers, neuropeptide Y, anthropometric measurements, and appetite in obese or overweight individuals with fruitful effect as antiobesity medicament.(123) A randomized clinical trial was performed using 62 to evaluate the efficacy and tolerability of a food supplement (FS) containing *Citrus limon* L. Osbeck and *Vitis vinifera* L. extracts, hesperidin from *Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck, and chromium, in individuals with impaired fasting blood glucose with isocaloric diet significantly improved glucose and lipid metabolism (124). Daily ingestion of orange juice in metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) has improved liver function in Sixty-two men and women aged 30-65 with MASLD (Controlled Attenuation Parameter (125). Orange juice intake improved depressive symptoms in young adults with MDD (major depressive disorder) (126). In another study consumption of citrus fruit has shown reduce risk for the development of gastric cancer as well as esophageal cancer.(127). TCM therapy shows a superior effective rate and cure rate compared with those in prokinetic agents in the treatment of FD of liver-stomach disharmony syndrome.(128) LI13109F is a novel herbal composition containing the extracts of *Boswellia serrata* gum resin and *Aegle marmelos* fruit in 56-day placebo-controlled and randomized double blind study) on subjects with mild to moderate asthma could intervene asthmatic syndrome. (129) chamomile may have modest anxiolytic activity in patients with mild to moderate GAD (generalized anxiety disorder).(130). It has also proven effective in severe carpal tunnel syndrome.(131). Matricaria oil aromatherapy could found to intervene in symptoms

with acute coronary disease (132); MTC mouth rinse can be used as an effective adjunct during nonsurgical periodontal therapy for chronic periodontitis. (133), cyclic mastalgia (134), oral mucositis (135), knee osteoarthritis (136). *Andrographis paniculata* extract has shown effective as standard therapy or adjunct therapy in the treatment of malaria. (137) Kalmegh has proven effective in the treatment of infective hepatitis also.(138). It also alleviates fatigue in in patients with RRMS (relapsing-remitting multiple sclerosis) receiving interferon beta in comparison to placebo and only interferon beta treatment (139). Kanjang® tablets (standardized *Andrographis paniculata* extract) could ameliorate cold symptoms. (140). *A. paniculata* extract (HMPL-004) at a dose of 1,800 mg could alleviate acute ulcerative colitis syndrome. (141) Standardized *andrographis paniculate* extract has proved efficacy in improving immunomodulatory effects evidenced by its effects on immune cells and cytokines (142). AP extract significantly lowered HbA1c and fasting serum insulin in patients with type 2 diabetes.(143) Kan Jang®/Nergecov®, a herbal composition of *Andrographis paniculata* (Burm. F.) Wall. ex. Nees and *Eleutherococcus senticosus* (Rupr. & Maxim.) Maxim extracts proved to be useful in treating mild COVID-19 (144). HMPL-004, an extract of *Andrographis paniculate* could inhibits TNF- α and IL-1 β and ameliorate acute ulcerative colitis and the effect are comparable to patients treated with meselazine (145). Adaptra® Forte (combination of adaptogenic plant extracts from *Andrographis paniculata* and *Withania somnifera*) exhibited stress-protective activity (146). NXT15906F6 (TamaFlex™) a proprietary blend containing standardized *Tamarindus indica* seeds and *Curcuma longa* rhizome extracts and NXT19185 a combination of NXT15906F6 and an aqueous ethanol extract of *Garcinia mangostana* fruit rind was found to be useful in osteoarthritis. (147, 148, 149). Hyaluronate-based gel containing high molecular weight polysaccharides from *Tamarindus indica* proved to be effective in the treatment for genitourinary syndrome of menopause (GSM) (150). Forzeje, a vaginal suppository of herbal Persian medicine combination of *Tribulus terrestris*, *Myrtus commuis*, *Foeniculum vulgare* and *Tamarindus indica* exhibited same effect as metronidazole in alleviating bacterial vaginitis. (151). Tamarind seed polypeptide 0.5% and 1% has

proven efficacy in dry eye syndrome. (152,153) Persian herbal medicines (Capsule number 1 contained extract of the *Glycyrrhiza glabra*, *Punica granatum*, and *Rheum palmatum*, and the second capsule was filled by *Nigella sativa* powder) could ameliorate dyspnoea and improve respiratory rate in COVID-19 patients. (154). Combination of fermented milk containing *L paracasei* and *G glabra* reduced *H pylori* density and improved histologic inflammation in *H pylori* infected patients. (155) GutGard® is a flavonoid-rich, deglycyrrhizinated liquorice root extract could alleviate GERD syndromes (156). Iranian herbal preparation, Lax-Asab, contains equal amounts of *Cassia angustifolia* Vahl. (xiá yè fān xiè yè), *Mentha piperita* L. (hú jiāo bò hé), *Zingiber officinale* Rosc. (shēng jiāng), *Glycyrrhiza glabra* L. (gān cǎo) could ameliorate chronic constipation. (157) Traditional medicines like *Atractylodes macrocephala*, *Poria cocos*, *Coix lacryma-jobi*, *Astragalus membranaceus*, *Glycyrrhiza uralensis* and *Panax ginseng* have reported inhibitory effects on nausea and vomiting (or its animal equivalent), regulation of gastrointestinal motility, gastroprotective effects and antioxidant actions (158). GutsyGum(tm), a chewing containing calcium carbonate, with a proprietary blend of licorice extract, papain, and apple cider vinegar (GiGs®) has shown to alleviate symptoms of heartburn and acid reflux.(159)

CONCLUSION

This review is a compilation of experimental data obtained from literature spanning more than 10 years of search. As the result implies in the four families abundant secondary metabolites are alkaloids, flavonoids, coumarins, chalcones, glycosides. Although the work was set based on the evaluation of anti *Helicobacter pylori* activity, a general clinical efficacy study of most important plants has also been documented.

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